

Effect of Parental Background on Study Habits among High School Students

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to understand the effect of parental background on the study habits of high school students. It included 100 students selected from Nalanda district of Bihar, who were aged 16 to 18 years. "Vijaya Lakshmi and Shruti Narayan Study Habit Scale and PDS were used for data collection." This study looked at factors such as the father's education and occupation and tried to know how these factors affect the study habits of students. The results show that students whose families are financially strong and educated study more disciplined. Such students use time properly and have more interest and motivation in their studies. On the other hand, students whose families are financially weak have difficulty concentrating and studying regularly. This study shows that parental support and attention to children's studies are important in improving their study habits.

Introduction

Study habits mention several methods and practices that are considered important for students' academic performance. Study habits are the methods someone uses to study. These are habits that students develop during their school years. Without good study habits, no student can achieve success. Students adopt these methods to learn systematically and efficiently when they can. Developing

good study habits by properly utilising library resources helps students learn how to study effectively, resulting in improved academic performance. Good study habits help students achieve good academic results, while poor study habits lead to distraction and lack of concentration. The approach with which a student approaches his studies largely determines his level of academic achievement. The preparation and learning strategies thoughtfully developed and adopted by students play a big role in improving their academic performance. Study habits are one of the biggest factors affecting students' academic achievements. If its importance is ignored by students, teachers, administrators, parents, school counsellors, and the government, the likelihood of poor performance of students in internal and external exams will increase and this situation will become more serious. According to Mark and Howard (2009), one of the biggest challenges to student success is the absence of good or effective study habits. They believe that if students develop better study habits and discipline, they will be able to excel in their academic endeavours. According to Kelly (2009), to be successful in their studies, students must be able to understand course material well, think deeply about it, and present it clearly in written or oral form. Most importantly, students must be able to develop good study habits. Many students think that spending more time studying is the most important thing, but in truth, good and effective study habits matter more. According to Husain (2000), study attitude refers to how students understand their studies. He believes that the right study approach increases the chances of academic success. The study method denotes what effective skills and techniques students know for studying and how they use them. A variety of study methods exist, and students can use these effective methods and skills according to their learning trends.

On the other hand, study habits can greatly affect students' academic performance. If not properly taken care of, it can negatively impact students' performance (Ebele & Olofu, 2017). Having good study habits is important for students to succeed in life, as these habits help them acquire correct and useful knowledge. Lack of these habits can lead to students' poor performance in school (Kaur & Pathania, 2015). Study habits mean that a person makes a specific, regular, and uninterrupted time for learning. Without this, he cannot grow or reach his full potential. Study habits determine how much a person will learn, how much progress he will make, and how much success he will achieve in life. All these things depend on his study habits, which help him to move forward throughout his life. Study habits play a vital role in the development of knowledge and perceptual abilities. These habits determine how much a person will learn, how much progress he will make, and how much success he will achieve in life. In all aspects, it depends on the study habits of the individual. Therefore, it can be said that study habits are

deeply connected to academic and educational achievements. A habit is a behaviour that becomes automatic when repeated. It is an action that is performed regularly and according to a plan, which cannot be repeated anywhere else in life. A habit is performed without any conditions, excuses, or exceptions. It is a fixed and continuous process that becomes an integral part of a person's life. Study habits are the ways we study. These habits are often developed during our school years. Study habits can be 'good' or 'bad'. 'Good' habits are those that help us get good grades, such as staying organized, taking good notes, reading textbooks, paying attention in class, and studying regularly. 'Bad' habits are those that take us away from success, such as skipping classes, not studying, watching too much TV, or playing video games instead of studying. Without good study habits, it becomes difficult for students to succeed. To be successful, students must be able to understand course material thoroughly, absorb it, and articulate that information in written or verbal form. Therefore, it is very important to develop good study habits. According to the American Journal of Psychology (1903), a habit is defined as: "a fixed way of thinking, wanting, or feeling acquired through repeated mental experience." a habit is a behaviour that we do over and over again until it becomes automatic for us. A habit is a pattern that is formed through repetition and often without our even realizing it. Study habits are a set of methods and routines that students follow in a good study environment. These habits are intended to increase the student's productivity, efficiency, and understanding while preparing for a particular exam. These habits are an organized effort to gather specific knowledge, which is following a set standard. It is a behaviour that appears even without conscious effort on the part of the learner. Study habits are a well-planned way of studying that helps students understand academic subjects and succeed in exams. These habits affect students' academic achievement and are interdependent. Students come from different backgrounds, which causes their achievement levels to vary. Some students have good study habits, while others have poor ones. Good study habits lead to academic success.

Definitions of Study Habits

Study habits are the degree to which a student regularly engages in a study routine. Study habits and attitudes refer to the willingness, openness, and receptiveness to learning. It means adopting a common or regular way of learning. Some definitions are given below.

★ **Hussain (2006)**, It may be stated: "Study habits refer to the tendency that students develop towards individual studies over some time."

★ **Crede (2008)**, defined study habits as external factors that aid the study process. These include good study routines, which include how often the student attends study sessions, reviews material, self-assessments, exercises, explains the material, and studies in a conducive environment.

★ **Azikiwe(1998)**, described study habits as “the adopted method and manner” through which students plan their studies after learning in class so that they can master the subject.

★ **Crede and Kuncel(2008)**, define “Study habits are study routines that include but are not limited to, the frequency of study sessions, review of the material, self-assessment, practising learned material, and studying in a conducive environment. Study habits are the behaviours and techniques that students use to learn, prepare for tests, and improve their academic performance. They are a combination of skills and study methods that can increase motivation and make studying more effective.”

There are two types of habits, good habits and bad habits. Study habits are good habits which are explained below.

Good Study Habits

Central Michigan University suggests some good study habits every student should have to achieve greater success academically.

1. Students have to avoid studying too much at once.
2. To develop good study habits, it is important to set a fixed time for studying. This helps maintain regularity and increases concentration.
3. One of the good study habits is to try to study at the same time every day. This creates a routine and makes the learning process more effective.
4. Good study habits require setting clear and specific goals, which gives direction to your studies.
5. An important aspect of study habits is to start studying on time as per the plan. This helps in maintaining discipline in your studies and helps you achieve your goals effectively.
6. Good study habits include working on the most difficult assignments first. This allows you to focus your energy and attention on the most challenging task at the beginning, making it easier to complete it.
7. Good study habits include reviewing your notes before starting an assignment. This helps you remember important information about the subject and helps you do the assignment better.

8. Good study habits include reviewing your school work on the weekend. This gives you a chance to understand the previous week's studies and prepare well for the next week.

Review of Related Literature

Hafiz Mudasir (2012) was presented to analyse the study habits and academic achievements of higher secondary students, boys and girls, from the science and arts streams. 80 students were randomly selected, out of which 40 students were from the science stream and 40 students were from the arts stream. The study used the study habit inventory constructed by Palsane and Sharma and the academic achievement of the students was assessed based on their percentage of marks obtained in the previous class. After collecting the data, it was tabulated and analysed. The results concluded that the study habits of girls were better than boys, while in terms of academic achievements, boys outperformed girls. However, in the case of arts stream students, no significant difference was found in the academic performance of male and female students.

Anshu Bala Singh (2019) presented a study for this study, 200 students of Allahabad city were selected by simple random sampling technique. A study habits list developed by Dr. M. Mukhopadhyay and Dr. D. N. Sansanwal was used for the research. The main findings of the study were as follows: (i) No significant difference was found in the study habits of students of working and non-working mothers, although the study habits of students of non-working mothers were better than those of working mothers. (ii) There was no significant difference in the study habits of students of urban and rural backgrounds, but the habits of urban students were better than those of rural students. (iii) No significant difference was observed between the study habits of male and female students.

Dr. Rifat Aara (2023) study habits refer to the permanent ways through which students acquire knowledge and skills. This research aimed to find out the relationship between study habits, intelligence and mental health of high school students. For this purpose, the descriptive method was used. The researcher included 200 high school students from Anantnag district of Jammu and Kashmir. The study used three major instruments for data collection: Study Habit Inventory (2005) developed by M. Mukhopadhyay and D.N. Sansanwal, the study used the Group Test of General Mental Ability by S. Jalota and the Mental Health Checklist by Pramod Kumar, analyzing data with descriptive and inferential statistics. Results showed no significant difference in the study habits of male and female or rural and urban students. However, a significant relationship was found between students' study habits and both their intelligence and mental health.

Clarke, C., et al (2024) this study aimed to identify the study habits of undergraduate and postgraduate students at Trinity College Dublin and the factors influencing them. Two online surveys were conducted: one in April 2019 and the other in April 2020, when COVID-19 restrictions were in place. 1557 students participated in the 2019 survey, while 1793 students participated in the 2020 survey. Most students reported using caffeine, studying in the library, changing sleep patterns and exercising to improve their academic performance. In the 2020 survey, 91% of students reported experiencing difficulties studying due to COVID-19. The study concluded that the college environment can play an important role in improving students' learning and well-being, especially during challenges such as the pandemic.

Chikaodili Benedine Nwizuzu (2024) conducted a study in this study, 400 students were selected based on gender and region (urban/rural), and data was collected through a self-designed questionnaire. The results showed that there was a moderate positive correlation ($r = .456$) between study habits and academic performance. This correlation was low ($r = .398$) among male students, while it was moderate ($r = .495$) among female students. A moderate positive correlation was also found among urban and rural students ($r = .455$ and $r = .453$). It was concluded that effective study habits, regardless of gender and region, are essential for improving academic performance. The study recommended targeted interventions and further investigation.

Objective of the Study

1. To examine the effect of a father's education and occupation on the study habits of students.

Hypothesis of the Study

- 1. Father's Educational Qualification:** The educational qualification of the father can affect the study habits of the students. If the father is educated, he motivates his children to study and provides a good study environment. This can help the children develop better study habits and achieve academic achievements. *Therefore, It was hypothesised that there will be a significant difference between the father's education and the study habits of students.*
- 2. Father's Occupation:** A father's job can influence students' study habits. If a father's job is stable and supportive, he can motivate children to study. In addition, working fathers can help their children understand the importance of time management and hard work, which can help

children develop better study habits. *Therefore, It was hypothesised that there will be a significant difference between the father's occupation and the study habits of students.*

Method of the Study

- **Sample:** The total sample was comprised of schools in the (Nalanda district of Bihar) with *an age range of 16 to 18 years*. The whole sample consists of a total of 100 students. To select the sample purposive sampling technique was used in the present study.

Tools of the Study

The following tools were used in the present study which is given below.

- **Personal Data Schedule (PDS, Self-made):**

A personal data sheet (PDS) is a document that a researcher uses to collect information about an individual's details, like sex, educational background, occupation etc. It provides complete information about individuals in the research context so that researchers can easily understand his/her importance.

- **Study Habits Inventory (SHI):**

The Study Habit Inventory was created by Dr. Vijaya Lakshmi and Dr. Shruti Narain and it is a 5-point scale for measuring the study habits of high school students, in this inventory consists of 38 statements divided into 4 dimensions.

Statistical Technique Used

- To test the hypothesis, an independent t-test was applied to the distribution of data.

Analysis and Interpretation

For the analysis of data, the data collection was tabulated.

Hypothesis 1. Significance of difference between the father's education and the study habits of students.

Table -1: Showing the significance of the difference between the father’s education and the study habits of students.

Sl. No.	Group	N	Mean	SD	t-between	t-ratio	df	P-value
A	Illiterate	48	111.79	14.61	A&B	3.568	79	< 0.001
B	Matric to Intermediate	33	124.03	15.49	A&C	4.521	65	< 0.001
C	Graduation to above	19	128.68	11.33	B&C	1.142	50	N.S

It is obvious from Table 1 that the statistical analysis of the father's educational background on students' study habits. The compared groups are divided based on the father's education level (illiterate, matriculation to intermediate and graduation to above), with the number of students (N) mean, study habit score, standard deviation (SD), t-ratio, degrees of freedom (df) and p-value. The mean score of students with illiterate fathers is 111.79. at the same time, the mean score of students whose fathers are educated from matriculation to intermediate is 124.03, which is significantly higher than the mean of the illiterate group. The t-ratio between these two groups shows that this difference is statistically significant. On the other hand, the mean score for students whose fathers have graduated or above is 128.68. While this score is higher than the other two groups, the t-ratio does not show any significant statistical difference when compared to this group. In this table students whose fathers have higher education levels also have better study habits this is visible in the increasing average marks from Group A to Group C. Therefore, it can be stated that “there is a significant difference between the father’s education and the study habits of students. Hence the hypothesis is retained.

Hypothesis 2. Significance of difference between the father’s occupation and the study habits of students.

Table- 2: Showing the significance of the difference between the father's occupation and the study habits of students.

SI No.	Group	N	Mean	SD	t-between	t- ratio	df	P- value
A	Agriculture	53	115.83	16.52	A&B	0.547	84	N.S
B	Business	33	117.82	16.17	A&C	2.224	65	< 0.05
C	service	14	126	8.11	B&C	1.791	45	N.S

It is obvious from Tale 2. This table compares the study habits of students from different parental backgrounds, such as agriculture, business, and the service sector. This study found a statistically significant difference in the study habits of students from agriculture and service backgrounds (A & C), with the mean score of students from service backgrounds 126 being higher than that of students from agriculture backgrounds 115.83. This suggests that students from service backgrounds may have better study habits than those from agricultural backgrounds. The mean score of students with a business background is 117.82, which is higher than an agriculture background (A and B), but this difference is not statistically significant. In this table students whose fathers have higher income levels also have better study habits this is visible in the increasing average marks from Group A to Group C. Therefore, it can be stated that “there is a significant difference between the father’s occupation and the study habits of students. Hence the hypothesis is retained.

Conclusions

- It is found that there is a significant difference between the father's education and the study habits of students. It is also observed that students whose fathers are more educated (graduate or above) have better study habits. On the other hand, students with uneducated fathers have lower study habits scores. It is also found that there is a significant relationship between father's education and students' study habits. Also, students whose fathers are graduates or above have higher average scores than students whose fathers' education level is uneducated to matriculation. Students with highly educated fathers have better study habits.
- It is found that there is a significant difference between the father's occupation and the study habits of students. Students whose fathers are in the service sector or professional jobs show better study habits. On the other hand, those students whose fathers are in less stable or unskilled jobs have lower study habits scores. This shows that the father's occupation affects student's study habits.

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